

Taxonomy of Operations in the Context of FAIR Digital Objects

Nicolas Blumenröhr, Andreas Pfeil, Thomas Jejkal, Rainer Stotzka
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology

July 7, 2023

1 Motivation

Operations in the context of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) [1] are typically initiated by a digital client and can be executed by the client or a server. These operations act on the FDO records, the data they represent, or the services involved. They are deterministic, capable of creating, modifying, transporting, and deleting digital entities. These processes essentially build on top of the CRUD operations (Create, Read, Update, Delete), a concept well-known in computer science. However, working with FDOs will require more complex operations that extend towards FAIRness [2] of the digital contents.

To help understanding these complex operations, we have drafted a first taxonomy. This classification will assist in identifying the operations required for specific tasks. The operations are divided into two main categories. Firstly, there are operations that directly address the services providing infrastructure for the FDOs, such as repositories, data type registries and Persistent Identifier (PID) services. These operations help determining the nature and relevance of a service in relation to various FDO use cases. Furthermore, they alter the state of the service, by creating, modifying, or deleting its contents, including data that shall be represented as a FDO.

The second category addresses operations on FDOs. They are categorized into operations performed solely on the FDO record (kernel information), and the data represented as FDO. The record operations are further divided into five subcategories, with the basic operations that are more related to the state of the record

within its registry, rather than focusing on the contents. The other four categories address different requirements for using the FDOs that are resolved by consulting their kernel information. Primarily, these operations facilitate decision-making about whether and how to proceed with a particular FDO, especially before conducting more resource-intensive tasks related to the represented data. The data operations are again divided into two sub-categories: operations that can be performed on the data regardless of their type, and those that are dependent on the type of the data.

The category for type-dependent operations builds multiple sub-categories, each of them containing further divisions, reflecting the ongoing evolution of FDO usage and operations. By categorizing type-dependent operations, the taxonomy also contains an overview of possible FDO types. However, this taxonomy isn't directly addressing these types. Instead, it defines which operations apply to data with a certain type characteristic, as represented by the FDOs. The taxonomy includes branches relevant to our use cases. This offers a foundation for extending it by other operations within the taxonomy, which will continue to grow as more use cases for FDOs are defined. Furthermore, existing categories may be extended to provide more specific variants of the existing operations, e.g., operations for data storage systems could be narrowed down to the nature of a particular service. Each category and corresponding operations are defined in the following passage. Some of these are more general definitions for operations that have already been described in service documentations (e.g., Digital Object Interface Protocol Specification V2 [3] or elsewhere. These already existing operations can be assigned to one of the categories, or integrated as an extension. A detailed graphical representation of the taxonomy has been also provided for further clarification. For a better view, you can refer to the file titled "Taxonomy_of_Operations_for_FDOs_Graphic.pdf" accompanying this document.

2 Operations

This section includes the classification of operations in the taxonomy essential for FDOs and provides a comprehensive explanation of each.

2.1 Service Operations

These operations are performed on the services providing infrastructure for the FDOs, e.g., repositories, data type registries, digital objects- and PID services.

Data Storage Service Operations These operations are performed on the services that are used as storage systems for data that can be represented as FDO.

- **HELLO:** Enables a client to retrieve information about a service.
- **REGISTER_DATA_RESOURCE:** Registers a new data resource entry. Assigns a unique ID and additional administrative metadata that might be indexed.
- **UPLOAD_DATA:** Either registers a new resource entry or uses an existing resource entry and uploads the data that should be represented as FDO to this location. This will depend on the technical details of the service. In both cases, the operation assigns a reference (e.g., URL or service specific ID) to the data where it can be accessed from.
- **DOWNLOAD_RESOURCE_METADATA:** Uses the unique ID of the resource entry to retrieve its administrative metadata. May include filtering for metadata attributes.
- **SEARCH_RESOURCE_METADATA:** Searches for multiple resources based on specific administrative metadata characteristics.
- **MODIFY_RESOURCE_METADATA:** Uses the unique ID of the resource entry to modify its administrative metadata.
- **MODIFY_RESOURCE_ACCESS_CONTROL:** Uses the unique ID of the resource entry to modify the access control and set permissions for specific operations on the resource and its data.
- **DELETE_RESOURCE:** Uses the unique ID of the resource entry to delete it.

Data Type Registry Operations These operations are performed on services that define data types, i.e., the structure and format of data.

- **REGISTER_DATA_TYPE:** Registers a new data type entry and assigns a PID to it with the prefix of the naming authority.
- **DOWNLOAD_DATA_TYPE:** Uses the PID of a data type entry to retrieve its specification.
- **MODIFY_DATA_TYPE:** Uses the PID of a data type entry to modify its content.
- **DELETE_DATA_TYPE:** Uses the PID of a data type entry to delete it.

PID Service Operations These operations are performed on services that register FDO records and assign PIDs to them.

- **REGISTER_RECORD:** Validates the requested record against its profile, assigns a PID to this record with the prefix of the naming authority and registers it

2.2 FDO Operations

These operations are performed on all digital entities that are part of a FDO.

2.2.1 Record Operations/ Kernel Operations

These operations are solely performed on the FDO record.

Basic Operations These operations are performed on the records that are registered in a PID service.

- **DOWNLOAD_RECORD:** Used to download a FDO record to a permanent or temporary storage system. May include caching for data that has already been downloaded.
- **MODIFY_RECORD:** Uses the PID of the record to modify its content.
- **DELETE_RECORD:** Uses the PID of the record to delete it.

Reusability Operations These operations are used to evaluate whether a FDO is reusable in the context of the given use case.

- **VALIDATE_PROFILE:** Uses the attribute in the PID record referencing the Kernel Information Profile to get the profile specification from the Data Type Registry and to validate the attributes in the FDO record against this specification.
- **SEARCH_RECORD:** Searches and filters FDOs that match a specific pattern for one or more attributes in their FDO records.
- **EVALUATE_LICENSE:** Uses the attribute in the PID record that references the license to evaluate whether the data represented as the FDO has a license that makes it reusable for the application.
- **GET_TYPE:** Uses the attribute in the FDO record referencing the FDO type to resolve the referenced PID of the type FDO.

- **GET_LOCATION:** Uses the attributes in the PID record referencing the location of the data asset, as well as the access protocol (if provided), to evaluate the information where the data represented as the FDO is deposited at, whether it is accessible, and whether it is deposited in a trusted storage system.
- **DISPLAY_OPERATIONS:** Displays all FDOs representing implementations of a particular operation that can be performed on a FDO.

Collection Operations These operations are only used in the context of FDOs that represent collections of other FDOs, or are elements of a collection, and contain this information in their FDO records.

- **GET_COLLECTION_ELEMENT:** Uses the attribute in the FDO record that references the collection elements to resolve the referenced PID.
- **GET_COLLECTION:** Uses the attribute in the FDO record of a collection element that references its collection to resolve the referenced PID.

Linked Metadata Operations These operations are used in the context of FDOs that represent metadata beyond the kernel information for another FDO or have the reference to another FDO that represents a digital object containing additional metadata. Both can apply for the same FDO.

- **GET_DESCRIBING_OBJECTS:** Uses the referencing attribute to other FDOs that contain additional metadata to resolve their PIDs.
- **GET_DESCRIBED_OBJECTS:** Uses the referencing attributes to other FDOs which are described by additional metadata to resolve their PIDs.

Type specific operations These operations are performed on records that contain information about the type of another FDO.

- **EVALUATE_MIME_TYPE:** Evaluates the mime-type attribute.
- **DOWNLOAD_SCHEMA:** Uses the referencing attribute to the schema on which the corresponding data is based to download it.

2.2.2 Data Operations

These operations are performed on data that is represented as a FDO.

Type Independent Operations These operations can be performed on the data deposited in a data storage system independent from its FDO type.

- **UPLOAD_DATA_VERSION:** Uploads a new version of the data in the same resource entry, without modifying the old version of the data, but modifying its resource metadata.
- **DOWNLOAD_DATA:** Uses the location reference to access and download a copy of the data to a permanent or temporary storage system. A particular version of the data can be addressed. May include caching for data that has already been downloaded.
- **MODIFY_DATA:** Modifies a particular data asset directly in the storage system, which might also modify the metadata of its record entry.
- **MOVE_DATA:** Moves a particular data asset within the storage system, which doesn't modify the data asset or its metadata directly but alters the reference to its location.
- **DELETE_DATA:** Deletes a particular data asset permanently from the data storage, including its metadata, making its reference invalid.

Type Dependent Operations These operations on the data are dependent on the FDO type. As the levels within this category can be very deep, they are no longer reflected by the levels of subdivision in the text. Please refer to the corresponding diagram for an overview.

Semantic data operations These operations are used on data of which the content refers to any kind of semantic data.

Metadata Operations These operations are used on data that contains relevant information about other data assets that supports or enables their use.

Schema-less Metadata Operations These operations are used on metadata assets that are not based on a particular schema.

- **SEARCH_MD:** Searches (indexed) metadata documents based on specific parameters and filters for documents and their contents that correspond to the request.

Schema-based Metadata Operations These operations are used on metadata assets that are based on a particular schema that defines their content, attribute types, and hierarchy.

- **SEARCH_MDSCH:** Searches the (indexed) metadata document based on specific parameters that correspond to specific fields or properties defined by its schema, and filters for documents and their contents that correspond to the request.
- **VALIDATE_SCHEMA_MDSCH:** Validates the format and structure of a metadata document against its schema.

Publication Metadata Operations These operations are used on metadata assets that particularly contain content about scientific publications.

- **EXPORT_CITATION_PUB:** Exports the citation extract from a metadata document that describes a scientific publication.

Linked Data Operations These operations are used on data that contains content referring to the conventions of Linked Data.

- **EVALUATE_LINKED_DATA_LIN:** Uses a reference to a Linked Data asset to evaluate its content and possibly proceeds using new references to evaluate more Linked Data content based on specific criteria.

Knowledge Graph Data Operations These operations are used on data that contains content corresponding to a knowledge graph.

Ontology Data Operations These operations are used on data that contains content corresponding to an ontology.

Image Data Operations These operations are performed on static visual data that is composed of pixels, mathematical equations, or geometric shapes.

Raster Graphic Data Operations These operations are used on data where the image is composed of individual pixels.

- **EXPORT_METADATA_RAS:** Accesses the metadata that is contained within the image file itself and converts it into a serializable format that is returned.

- **GET_SIZE_RAS:** Gets and returns the dimensions along each axis of an image in pixels from a processable data structure.
- **RESIZE_RAS:** Makes a copy of the image, resizes the copy along each axis using a specific resizing algorithm and returns it.
- **NORMALIZE_RAS:** Makes a copy of the image, scales the pixel intensity values of the copy to a desired range, and returns it.
- **GROUP_RAS:** Groups multiple images that are located on the same storage system into a common data structure that makes these images processable as a unit.

Vector graphic Data Operations These operations are used on data where the image is composed of mathematical equations or geometric shapes.

Collection Data Operations: Are performed on data that is a collection for other data assets, or on data that is an element of a data collection.

- **SEARCH_COL:** Searches the (indexed) collection based on specific parameters and filters for collection elements that correspond to the request.
- **GET_SIZE_COL:** Retrieves the number of collection elements and their file size that are contained within a data collection.
- **INSERT_ELEMENT:** Inserts data as a new collection element into the data collection.
- **MODIFY_ELEMENT_COL:** Modifies an existing collection element.
- **DELETE_ELEMENT_COL:** Permanently deletes a particular collection element.

Medical and Materials Science Domain Data Operations: Are performed on data that was created by and is associated with activities in the medical and materials science domain, and is stored in domain specific file formats.

- **EXPORT_IMAGE_MEDMA:** Extracts the image component from a medical file, which is then returned in a raster or vector graphic type format.
- **EXPORT_METADATA_MEDMA:** Extracts the metadata header from a medical file, which is then returned in a serialized format.

Tabular Data Operations: Are performed on tabular data that is either contained within a file or exists in a database.

Scripting and Programming Language Data Operations: Are performed on data of which the content refers to a scripting or programming language, or which is required for executing code.

Workflow Data Operations: Performed on data that contains a workflow, i.e., a sequence of interconnected tasks, activities, or steps that are performed to accomplish a specific goal or achieve a desired outcome.

Video Data Operations: Are performed on video data that contains dynamic visual data, i.e., a series of frames or images that can be played in succession over time.

Compressed Data Operations: Are performed on data that has been encoded in a more concise form to reduce the number of bits or bytes required to represent the information.

Audio Data Operations: Are performed on auditive data, i.e., the analog audio waveforms captured from various sources of auditory information.

Acknowledgements This work has been supported by the research program 'Engineering Digital Futures' of the Helmholtz Association of German Research Centers and the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration Platform.

References

- [1] Erik Schultes and Peter Wittenburg. *FAIR Principles and Digital Objects: Accelerating Convergence on a Data Infrastructure*. 07 2019.
- [2] M. D. Wilkinson et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3, 2016.
- [3] Digital object interface protocol specification. https://www.dona.net/sites/default/files/2018-11/DOIPv2Spec_1.pdf, 2018.

- Color Code:**
- CREATE-based
 - RETRIEVE-based
 - UPDATE-based
 - DELETE-based

